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Project Management Software Tools for Education

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ABSTRACT

Most universities pursue efforts to provide students with the best skills to tackle the employment market by offering subjects that fulfill market needs. By doing so, young engineers will find on the job site a reduction on its learning curve when confronted with similar subjects or even tools. Project management tools are increasingly used in the IT Market but unfortunately, are not widely taught or even applied in the academic context. In order to encourage the teaching of such tools and by having in mind the sustainability of engineering education, we have done a survey on well referenced free project management tools that have the capability to follow some of the PMBOK practices. In this context, we tested and compared the following project management tools: Bitrix24, Zoho, and Wrike.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability and Engineering Education, University-Business Cooperation and Engineering Skills.

Keywords: Project Management, Free Tools, PMBOK

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of collaborative tools, such as project management tools, have shown greater success in software delivery due to the proper planning that project management tools offer. In a time where only 16,2% of software are successfully delivered on time and on budget, the Standish Group [1], a research advisory organization that focuses on software project performance by discovering why projects fail and how they can better succeed, states that one of the top 4 project success factors is the proper planning.

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IPM Global, a Project Management software development company integrated with Microsoft, SAP and Sage managed by directors working in this field for over 20 years advertises that the use of automated project management tools not only reduces project risks but also enables several other advantages like the centralization of project documentation and the standardization of processes [2]. Allured by the benefits of project management tools, IT companies have been increasingly using project management tools to support project management and to track software development.

These project management tools are used by all project's stakeholders including software developers - one of the most likely jobs for young computer science engineers – to report their work. Therefore, disclosing project management tools that might be used by students' future employers it is promoting the teaching of actual professional practices in computer science engineering and better prepare computer science engineers for the competitive IT market [3]. By doing so, young engineers will find on the job site a reduction on its learning curve when confronted with similar project management tools, and consequently, its higher education will be certainly well perceived by the employers.

Even though project management tools are used by all project's stakeholders. Its principal administrator is the project manager who can follow diverse management practices like the project management body of knowledge guide PMBOK [4]. This guide is a worldwide de facto standard in the project management field that gathers a sum of good practices within the profession of project management.

Nowadays, there is a varied choice of project management tools. Thus, choosing the right project management tool to teach can be overwhelming. In this context, we are interested in the evaluation of free project management tools - most universities have limited budgets - with the capability to follow some of the PMBOK practices – most likely used by IT Companies. Furthermore, we have focused on proprietary tools that have a free version with an unlimited time of use, to enable students to learn and use it at the university. The drawback of these free proprietary versions is the limitation of features compared to the complete paid version. On the other hand, the significant reduction of the young engineers' learning curve on the job site, when confronted with the same tool, is the biggest counterpart and advantage - basic features are displayed in the same manner than the paid version.

Therefore, this paper aims to guide Professor's choice by presenting our evaluation of the following free project management tools: Zoho [5], Bitrix24 [6] and Wrike [7]. These tools were selected due to the good feedback that the IT consultant Capterra gave in 2017 [8], as well as its wider coverage on PMBOK's suggested features. By Capterra's ranking, Bitrix24 stands at the 1st position, Wrike at the 5th and Zoho at the 8th position but the PMBOK guidelines were not considered for the ranking of these tools which leads us to a deeper assessment.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. In section 2, project management tools are described regarding its principal features and its strengths and weaknesses are exposed. In section 3, the methodology used to test the tools is disclosed. In section 4, the tool's comparison is presented and the best project management tool to teach is suggested. In section 5, related work is briefly presented and finally, in section 6, conclusions and future work are exposed.

2 PROJECT MANAGEMENT TOOLS

In this section, we describe the selected tools: Zoho [5], Bitrix24 [6] and Wrike [7]. In order to portray these tools, we describe its principal features as well as its main strengths and weaknesses.

2.1 Zoho

Zoho [5] is actually used by 15 million users worldwide and has a set of free features that can be considered, among others tools in the market, pretty complete. Its main free features are user assignment, user profile configuration, file upload – up to 10MB - and generation of notifications. Notifications can be sent to the user's e-mail or to the online platform wall, which enables to at a glance see all recent activities.

In spite of not having a tracking of the worker's time spent on its task neither a CRM, all basic features from the PMBOK guide exists: tracking a project with a Gantt chart, managing tasks and subtasks with dependencies and priorities, graphically visualize the tasks and the whole project achievements, and provide the communication between stakeholders.

During our tools' evaluation, we have seen that Zoho presented a better dashboard than Bitrix24 and Wrike. In fact, in an appealing graphic form, Zoho displays the percentage of tasks, subtasks and project lifecycle phases that are completed, as well as the percentage of completion of the overall project.

In *Fig. 1* we present the interface of the Zoho tool. At the top center of the print screen, we can see the name of the project that we have created to test this tool. At below left we can see the menu of the tool and at below right a part of the Zoho dashboard where in this case the number of open, closed and total of tasks of a milestone is seen graphically with a donut chart and the task completion percentage with a line chart.

Fig. 1. Zoho Dashboard

The major advantages of this tool are:

The existence of a dashboard; The unlimited number of users that can be assigned; The error feature – project errors can be registered; The unlimited time of use.

Its major weaknesses are:

The number of projects that can be managed - in the free version only 1 to 5 project; The unavailability to track the worker's work time - the tool does not have a timer to track the labor-time.

2.2 Bitrix24

The Bitrix24 [6] is one of the most complete free project management tools seen on market and is also well classified by the IT consultant Capterra [8].

It covers most of the features that we have analyzed but it does not have the capability to graphically visualize the tasks or the whole project achievement, nor set prioritization on the tasks to be done.

Among the tools presented in this paper, it is the only one which has a timer to track the labor-time. This is useful to monitor and control the time taken to execute project's tasks and consequently, manage the labor-time.

The Bitrix24 interface is shown in *Fig. 2* with the time tracking active: at left, Bitrix24 menu is shown, at center, task's time management is seen and in the top menu, at right of the presented hours, the timer is shown.

Fig. 2. Bitrix24 Time Tracking

The principal advantages of its use are:

Appealing interface; Wide set of features; Having a Customer Relationship Management feature (CRM) – this system allows to manage business relationships; Having a labor-time tracking and an unlimited time of use.

Its principal weaknesses are:

It is not possible to set task's prioritization and it does not have a dashboard to in a glance track the progress of the project.

2.3 Wrike

The project management tool Wrike [7] has been named a 2014 “Cool Vendor” in social software and collaboration by the IT Consultant Gartner, and many renowned companies, like PayPal and HTC, relies on it.

One of our interests to analyze this project management tool was its possibility to integrate with the Windows, the most common operating system used by IT companies, through the Microsoft Office 365 version [9]. Therefore, it is a project management tool that goes with the aiming of this paper – the disclosure of project management tools that are more likely professionally used by IT companies to promote the teaching of actual professional practices.

Nevertheless, during our tool's evaluation and comparison, we have seen that Wrike covers fewer features in its free version than Zoho and Bitrix24. Furthermore, the most important ones, like the Gantt Chart, is only available for 30 days. Therefore, we can say that it is a limited platform in its free version. However, its simplicity and good capacity on performing are better than the other two in the sense that all covered features were highly scored during our experiment.

In *Fig. 3* the Wrike interface can be seen: at left we have the Wrike menu and at right, its Gantt chart where dependencies are seen between the inserted tasks.

Fig. 3. Wrike Gantt Chart

The main advantages of the Wrike tool are:

The functional stability in its features, in part due to its simplicity; The unlimited dependencies that can be created between inserted tasks; The ease of use.

Its main weaknesses are:

Feature's limitation; The 30 days' time limit for the use of the Gantt Chart feature.

3 TOOL TESTING METHODOLOGY

By considering most online free project management tools, a set of common features was identified. To those features, we added some of the PMBOK basic methods, specifically the ones suggested for project time management. Afterward, we have tested each tool regarding the existence, the utility and the ease of use of each selected feature, and have evaluated it by assigning a score from 1 to 5 to each feature. Finally, we have added up the features scores and the best tool was identified. This testing methodology was inspired by the Project Management tool selecting criteria proposed by the author Lornel Rivas et al. for small to medium enterprises [10].

For the scoring of the assessed features we have defined the following criteria:

0 = The tool does not have the feature; **1** = The tool has the feature, but it is not useful and its use is difficult; **2** = The tool has the feature, but it is not useful in spite of its ease of use; **3** = The tool has the feature, it is useful but it is difficult to use it, not well conceived or does not work properly; **4** = The tool has the feature, it is useful and easy to use; **5** = The tool has the feature, it is useful and intuitive.

The selected features that we have used to assess the free version of Zoho [5], Bitrix24 [6] and Wrike [7] were:

Add users - possibility to add at least 3 users to the project management tool.

User Profile - possibility to configure user's different accesses to the online platform.

Task Timer - tracking of the worker's time spent on its tasks (employees can start in the platform a timer function by the time a task is started).

Chat - possibility to have written online meetings or discussions with the added users.

Upload up to 10 MB - capability to store documents, at least up to a total of 10 MB size, on the online platform to share among added users.

Manage 12 tasks - capability to manage at least 12 tasks that have a duration bigger than one day long.

Manage 4 subtasks - capability to manage at least 4 subtasks.

Task dependency - dependency between tasks and subtasks to establish an execution order to ensure that team members follow the project sequence that was initially planned.

% of task's conclusion - capability to track the achievement of the tasks by graphically consulting the percentage of its conclusion.

Task prioritization - capability to define tasks' priority and track it graphically.

CRM - Customer Relationship Management feature that provides the possibility to record, manage and analyze customer interactions and throughput of the customer lifecycle [11].

% of project's conclusion - capability to track the achievement of the whole project.

Gantt chart - capability to graphically manage the tasks of the project. A Gantt chart represents schedule information where activities are listed on the vertical axis, dates are shown on the horizontal axis, and activity durations are shown as horizontal bars placed according to start and finish dates [4].

Notifications - informs when a task is assigned or overdue by email and/or by adding a post on the online tool wall.

4 TOOLS COMPARISON

By following the tool testing methodology presented in section 3 we have assessed the Zoho [5], Bitrix24 [6] and Wrike [7] Project Management tool and built a comparative analysis that Table 1 depicts.

Table 1. Project Management Tools' Comparison

Features	Tools		
	Zoho	Bitrix24	Wrike
Add users	5	5	5
User Profile	5	3	5
Task Timer	0	5	0
Chat	5	5	5
Upload up to 10 MB	3	5	5
Manage 12 tasks	4	5	5
Manage 4 subtasks	3	5	5
Task dependency	5	3	5
% of task's conclusion	4	0	0
Task prioritization	5	0	0
CRM	0	5	0
% of project's conclusion	5	0	0
Gantt chat	5	5	2
Notifications	5	5	5
TOTAL	54	51	42

The focus of this paper is to assess free project management tools; thus, the selected features were analyzed and tested regarding its capabilities to perform freely. It is important to say that these selected tools are basically proprietary platforms, which means that are monthly paid, but all of them have a free version, with less functionalities than the paid one that is worth to analyze and consider because of its unlimited time of use. Its limitation is the working context in which they can perform.

During the assessment of the selected tools we have identified the following limitations for each tool:

Zoho - Only works for 1 to 5 projects depending on the number of users added - for every person assigned to the platform one project is added, up to 5 projects. Which means that all tasks can only be related to 1 to 5 projects regardless the number of

users assigned. It can integrate with Google Drive or Dropbox so the 10MB file storage limitation seen in the free version is not an issue, in our point of view.

Bitrix24 - Works with up to 12 users and 5 tasks dependencies. Other than that, its free version is very interesting: it has a CRM and it provides a good user experience given by its appealing interface. Its biggest drawback is its impossibility to define unlimited task dependencies. Furthermore, its users' profile configuration is very limited.

Wrike - Works with up to 5 users, independently the number of task dependencies recorded or projects mounted. The major drawback is the lack of features, even after migrating to the paid version, comparing to Bitrix24, or even Zoho. The other important drawback of this tool is the 30 days time limit for the use of the Gantt Chart feature, which was the reason for the 2 score given.

By considering the features scores presented in Table 2, Zoho finished with 54 points, Bitrix24 with 51 points and Wrike with 42 points. By weighting them up with their working limitation and user experience, Zoho was identified as the best tool to teach among the ones tested. Zoho election was not only based on its higher score, but also on its capability to better track the scheduled work through the tasks prioritization and project follow up that this tool provides.

5 RELATED WORK

There are actually various published papers in the field of project management tools that can be classified in one of the following types:

- Disclosure of Project Management Tools – popular [12][13], open source or proprietary ones [14].
- Exhibition of open source tools capability analyses vs. proprietary ones [15] [14].
- Presentation of tool's selection models – [16], AHP model [17] or specified to small and medium enterprises (SMEs) [10].
- Importance of use [18] [19].

This paper falls into the disclosure of project management tools but in the area of studying proprietary project management tools that have a free version that follows some of the techniques suggested by the PMBOK standard. From the best of our knowledge, no other paper approached this topic.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper enabled the identification of the project management tool Zoho, among the Bitrix24 and the Wrike solution, as a suitable tool to teach future computer science engineers. Its free version and wider coverage in features that support PMBOK techniques makes it suitable for universities with budget limitations and for future computer science engineers that aim to thrive in renowned IT companies since they usually follow the PMBOK management techniques. Thus, disclosing the selected project management tools was promoting the teaching of actual professional practices and better prepare students to the competitive IT market.

The selected tools' evaluation was only made upon its free version, the eventual gap between free and paid versions, regarding features availability, can be bigger in one tool than in another. Thus, the selection of a project management tool with the only purpose of reducing students' learning curve at the job site, could eventually lead to the identification of another solution. However, we have found, during our testing period, that Zoho offered a bigger functional feature stability than Bitrix24, which justifies the minimal score that separates one tool from the other. As future work, we intend to evaluate the complete paid version of the selected project management tools.

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